

MANUFACTURING OF SANDWICH LAMINATES WITH PERFORATED CARBON NANOTUBE FOREST CORE

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1. Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been incorporated in composites to increase strength, stiffness, damping, and electrical and thermal conductivities [1-3]. However, most commercial CNT nanocomposites have CNTs arranged in random orientations. In recent research, aligned CNTs have been integrated into fiber composites via lamination [4] or direct growth of CNTs on fibers [5], and have shown promising enhancements in interlaminar toughness [4, 5], and electrical and thermal conductivities [6].

In traditional laminated composites, the use of low-density sandwich layers such as honeycombs structures can achieve high bending stiffness and strength at low density, and enable energy absorption by plastic deformation of the honeycomb cells. For example, fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) honeycombs have been used for highway bridge decks [7], and aramid honeycomb structures have also been used for constrained layer damping in helicopter blades [8]. It has also been shown theoretically that honeycomb cores in sandwich beams exhibit better vibration and acoustic damping characteristics when compared to square cores [9].

Nevertheless, most cellular interlayers are made from bulk metals or engineered fibers. Micro-patterning of vertically aligned CNTs offers potential to explore design of CNT forests as sandwich layers. In this paper we combine the concept of CNT nanocomposites with the honeycomb geometry, and demonstrate the construction of a laminate core comprising a polymer-infiltrated perforated CNT forest.

Exemplary CNT core laminates comprising thin metal face sheets are fabricated, and the stiffness and damping properties of the laminates in bending are presented.

2. Laminate Fabrication

2.1 Perforated Core Design

A perforated CNT forest was designed with 20 μm diameter holes that are hexagonally arranged with a center-to-center distance of 25 μm . This design ensured that there will be thorough infiltration of Al_2O_3 into the CNT forest when subjected to Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD), enabling mechanical reinforcement of the soft CNT forest. Our previous work showed that there is a finite penetration depth (approximately 5 μm) of ALD Al_2O_3 into CNT forests using normal ALD cycle parameters.

2.2 Catalyst Patterning and CNT Growth

The honeycomb CNT catalyst pattern was defined on a Silicon wafer by photolithography using a photoresist (SPR220 3.0). The CNT catalyst (10 nm Al_2O_3 /1 nm Fe) was then deposited via sputtering. The wafer was diced to 20mm by 20mm squares using a dicing saw and the wafer pieces were subjected to a lift off procedure to prepare them for CNT growth. The lift off procedure consisted of ultrasonication in acetone for 8 minutes twice then rinsing with isopropanol, then blow-drying with nitrogen.

The CNT forests were grown via thermal chemical vapor deposition (CVD) in a hot walled quartz tube furnace. The patterned catalyst on a Si substrate is

placed in the quartz tube and annealed for 10 minutes at 775 °C while flowing 100 sccm of H₂ and 400 sccm of He. C₂H₄ is used as the carbon source and 100 sccm is added to the total flow after the annealing step to facilitate CNT growth. The growth was stopped once the CNT forest has reached desired height. The height of CNT forests used in this study is approximately 100 μm. An SEM image of the perforated CNT layer is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. SEM image of a perforated CNT forest

2.3 Mechanical Reinforcement

As-grown CNT forests have low areal density (defined as the number of CNTs per unit area) close to 100 CNTs/μm². The Young's modulus of as-grown forests in compression is approximately 10 MPa and is governed by the bending of individual CNTs due to their low aspect ratio. In order to increase the stiffness of the CNT forest, the CNTs were reinforced with Al₂O₃. Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) is used to create a conformal coating of Al₂O₃ on the CNTs within the perforated forest microstructures. Each cycle of ALD deposits approximately 1.2 Å of Al₂O₃. The perforated CNT forests with various thicknesses of Al₂O₃ coatings are shown in Fig. 2. The number of cycles of ALD used in this study are 0, 20, 100, 400, 700 and 1000.

2.4 Polymer Infiltration and Lamination

Once the CNT forests were reinforced with Al₂O₃, the remaining spaces in the CNT forest were filled with polymer (e.g., polyurethane, PU). The polymer was drop-casted onto the CNT forest, and then the solvent was evaporated on a hotplate at 100 °C for 8 hours. The resulting film cross-sections are shown in Fig 3. For the CNT forests with less than 100 cycles of ALD reinforcement, the CNT forest undergoes

Fig. 2. Al₂O₃ reinforced perforated CNT forests with insets showing close ups. Number of ALD cycle: a) 0 cycle, b) 20 cycles, c) 100 cycles, d) 400 cycles, e) 700 cycles, and f) 1000 cycles

Fig. 3. Cross sections of Al_2O_3 reinforced perforated CNT forests after drop-casting PU. Number of ALD cycles: a) 0 cycle, b) 20 cycles, c) 100 cycles, d) 400 cycles, e) 700 cycles, and f) 1000 cycles

elastocapillary aggregation upon drop casting of PU due to the surface tension of the solvent in the PU solution. The walls of perforated CNT forests become thinner and bend/collapse from the vertical axis (Fig. 3a, 3b).

The resulting composite film is molded by applying heat and pressure to flatten the surface and squeeze out excess polymer. The hot-pressed film is delaminated by cracking the silicon substrate and carefully peeling away to create a freestanding nanocomposite film. The step-by-step illustration of composite film molding and delamination, and its effect is shown in Fig 4.

Last, the laminates were fabricated by stacking two stainless steel (Type 302) sheets and a freestanding nanocomposite film. The laminates were fixed together by heat pressing at 100 °C with the pressure of 0.5 MPa for 8 hours. Although 0.1 mm thick steel sheets and composite films were used to create the laminate, final laminate thicknesses are approximately 0.4 mm compared to the expected 0.3 mm, suggesting there are some manufacturing

defects such as air pockets, excess PU layer and slight curvature in the layers.

3. Laminate Properties

3.1 Measurement

The CNT/ Al_2O_3 /PU composite core laminates were characterized by a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (TA Instruments RSAIII) using a three point bending fixture. The distance between the supports was 10mm. For static flexural testing, the loading rate was 0.001 mm/sec, and for the Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) the range of frequencies used was 0.1-10Hz with the flexural strain amplitude of 0.02%.

3.2 Bending Stiffness

Analogous to Young's modulus, the flexural modulus, E_f , can be calculated by taking the ratio of the flexural stress, σ_f , and the flexural strain, ϵ_f . The flexural stress and strain can be obtained from the results and parameters of the flexural test as the following expressions (for beams with rectangular cross sections):

Fig. 4. a) Fabrication of freestanding nanocomposite film b) SEM image showing the cross section of a nanocomposite film with embedded CNT micropillars before and after applying heat and pressure to flatten the top surface.

Fig. 5. Flexural stress-strain curves of the fabricated laminates. Number of ALD cycles in the composite film damping layer: a) 0 cycle, b) 400 cycles, and c) 1000 cycles

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3FL}{2wt^2} \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

$$\epsilon_f = \frac{6dt}{L^2} \quad (\text{eq.2})$$

where F is the applied load, L is the distance between the supports, w is the width of the beam, t is the thickness of the beam and d is the displacement at the center of the beam. The flexural stress-strain curves of the laminates are shown in Fig 5 and the measured flexural modulus values are summarized in Table 1.

The flexural moduli of the fabricated laminates are comparable to that of the steel sheet with the same dimensions. Some degradation of the flexural modulus relative to the pure steel plates is expected, as the CNT/Al₂O₃/PU composite film is significantly softer than steel. Variations in the flexural moduli across different laminates are attributed to

compares them against those of a steel plate with same dimensions. The loss factors of the laminates are considerably higher than that of pure steel sheet, and the loss factor increases as the number of ALD cycles applied to the core increases. As the CNT forest core gets stiffer (as a result of the greater number of cycles of ALD) the shear in the PU matrix will be greater in magnitude since the strain in PU matrix will account for more of the strain caused by bending.

In order to design a laminate with desired damping characteristics, being able to predict the damping characteristics is essential. Analysis of constrained layer damping was first presented by Kerwin [10] and since then, many other models were developed [11]. We have used Kerwin's model to provide a quick validation of experimentally obtained values of damping of fabricated laminates. Kerwin's approach states that the loss factor of plates and beams with constrained layer damping is described by the following equation:

$$\frac{\eta}{\beta} = \frac{12(H_{31}^2/H_1^2) \left(\frac{K_3}{K_1}\right) [g/(1+g)^2]}{\left[1 + \left\{\frac{12(H_{31}^2/H_1^2) \left(\frac{K_3}{K_1}\right) g/(1+g)}{1 + \left(\frac{K_3}{K_1}\right) g/(1+g)}\right\} \left[1 + \left(\frac{K_3}{K_1}\right) g/(1+g)\right]^2\right]} \quad (\text{eq.3})$$

imperfections in lamination process and geometry of the layers (shearing of the steel sheets introducing some curvature). The hysteresis in the stress-strain curves increases as the number of ALD cycle increases suggesting that more energy is being dissipated with laminates with thicker Al₂O₃ coating in the core.

3.3 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

DMA was performed in the three point bending configuration to characterize the damping properties of the laminates. A steel plate with the same dimensions was also tested to serve as a baseline for comparison. Fig. 6. summarizes the dynamic mechanical properties (averaged over the tested frequency range, 0.1-10Hz) of the laminates and

where η is the loss factor of the beam/plate, β is the imaginary component of the complex shear modulus

Laminate Configuration (No. of ALD cycles)	Flexural Modulus (E _f , GPa)
Steel	5.89
CNT/PU	6.39
CNT/Al ₂ O ₃ /PU (20)	7.69
CNT/Al ₂ O ₃ /PU (100)	5.65
CNT/Al ₂ O ₃ /PU (400)	4.90
CNT/Al ₂ O ₃ /PU (700)	4.74
CNT/Al ₂ O ₃ /PU (1000)	5.69

Table 1. Flexural Moduli of fabricated laminates and steel sheet of same dimensions.

Fig. 6. DMA results of fabricated laminates versus number of ALD Al_2O_3 cycles for the perforated CNT core (averaged across the frequency range tested). The dashed lines are DMA results for a steel sheet having the same dimensions as the laminates.

of the constrained layer, H_{31} is the distance between the mid-planes of constraining layer and damped layer, H_1 is the thickness of the constraining layer, $K_{1,3}$ are the stretching stiffness ($= (EA)_{1,3}$) of constraining and damped layers, and g is the dimensionless shear parameter. The dimensionless shear parameter, g , is described by the following expression:

$$g = G / (k_B^2 K_3 H_2) \quad (\text{eq.4})$$

where G is the real component in the complex shear modulus, k_B is the wave number of the bending waves, and H_2 is the thickness of the constrained damping layer.

If we consider a 3 layer laminate with PU damping layer, using $G = 8.6 \text{ MPa}$ and $\beta=0.5$ (from previous characterization of PU film), the loss factor is calculated to be 0.093 by Kerwin's model. Assuming addition of perforated CNT forest does not change the shear modulus of PU film significantly, the calculated value of loss factor is consistent with the experimentally obtained value of 0.089 for the laminate with 0 cycles of ALD reinforcement.

Kerwin's model shows that the damping characteristics of constrained layer damped system depend largely on the geometry of the layers as well as the properties of the constituent materials. Previously conducted theoretical studies report loss factors of 0.07-0.10 for 100% coverage of a damping patch on a cylindrical shell [12], and 0.01

for a three-layer steel-rubber-steel sandwich beam [13]. The loss factors obtained in this study (0.09 - 0.13) compare favorably to these results.

4. Conclusions

We have successfully fabricated a sandwich laminate consisting of steel face sheets and Al₂O₃ reinforced CNT forest core, with the voids filled with PU. To ensure good contact between the core and the face sheets for good load transfer, the PU filling was molded to be flat and rid of excess PU layer on top beyond the top of the CNT forest. Three point bending flexural tests and DMA were performed to measure the mechanical properties of the fabricated laminates in bending. We have demonstrated an increase in loss factor without degradation in bending stiffness over pure steel plates, and the loss factor increases with increasing number of ALD cycles applied to the CNT core.

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